

CHALLENGES AND METHODS OF TEACHING ENGLISH TO LAW STUDENTS

Komila Sayfiyeva Kamolidinovna¹

¹ English teacher at Tashkent State Law University

k.sayfiyeva@tsul.uz

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5813083>

ARTICLE INFO

Received: 20th December 2021

Accepted: 25th December 2021

Online: 30th December 2021

KEY WORDS

Legal English, student, university, lawyer, legal profession, teacher, teaching, grammar, vocabulary, communicative competencies.

ABSTRACT

This article reveals topical problems of methodological developing and teaching English for law students specialties, as well as modern and innovative methods of teaching English for law students, the principles of selection teaching methods taking into account the specific needs of the students. The purpose of the study is to identify basic methodological approaches to teaching English for students of law universities in domestic and foreign literature. In conclusion, the author notes that in order to achieve the maximum effect, teaching English for legal purposes should be multidimensional, innovative and should be included classroom, independent and extracurricular work.

Introduction

The legal system of the Republic of Uzbekistan, as a rule, is formed on the basis of international legislative acts, for an objective understanding of which is necessary to study documents in English, which is international. In addition, Uzbek jurisdiction has many controversial issues. In the context of a certain court case, the study of similar situations from international and foreign practice can become a good tool for arguing the guilt or innocence of the persons involved in the case, and sometimes play a decisive role.

In this regard, in order to achieve success in their professional activities, students of legal specialties must necessarily know English at a level not lower than intermediate, have a stock of

professional vocabulary. At the same time, today in modern pedagogical theory and practice there is no unified comprehensive methodology for teaching students of legal specialties English, which significantly complicates the entire teaching process. In addition, the language, the language of legal terminology is constantly changing and need to be supplemented. That is why, university teachers are forced to constantly be in the search and adaptation of the developed methods to each specific case - to each specific set of students.

Research Methods

It should be noted that the selected research topic is relevant and appropriate for research in the context of this work, which determined the formulation of goals and objectives: The purpose of the work is

to identify the main methodological approaches to teaching English for law students in domestic and foreign literature. To achieve this goal during work, it is necessary to perform a number of tasks of the following character:

- to identify the key problems of the methodology of teaching English for students of legal specialties;
- consider teaching methods, the most often used in the universities of Uzbekistan;
- consider innovative teaching methods that are rarely used by the teachers of higher education;
- analyze traditional and innovative teaching strategies.

It is worth to mention that socialization problems are always relevant when learning a foreign language. Therefore, when teaching second language to law students, it should be taken into account that a modern specialist must have a level that would allow him to communicate, if necessary, with specialists from other countries. To do this, he must know the basics of grammar, but, most importantly, he must know the vocabulary of a legal orientation. Among the methods of teaching English for law students, there are both traditional and innovative ones.

Traditional teaching methods include:

- reading articles, news, theoretical material covering professional topics of legal discipline;
- retelling / narration of the studied theoretical topic of a particular research the question read in the article;

- study of legal professional vocabulary;
- analysis of normative legal acts in English (reading, translation, analysis, answers to questions that make it possible to understand how the student understood what he read);
- analysis of examples of judicial practice;
- listening to audio recordings of dialogues on topics, implying a discussion of certain legal issues.

The non-traditional teaching methods are:

- viewing documentary and fiction films in the classroom or on their own, after watching a series of tasks to assess how the student understood the events of the film;
- organization of dialogue sessions of various forms during which students are divided into groups and discuss certain topics of jurisprudence, determined by the teacher or chosen independently;
- Conversation clubs and other methods of extracurricular practice of speaking skills;
- project activities of students (Azizova.S.M, 2016, p.255).

Analysis and problems in teaching legal terms

One of the key problems of teaching professional English to modern students, i.e. in the context of students receiving higher education, incl. legal specialties, is a highly differentiated heterogeneity of knowledge of students entering universities. On the one hand, if we talk about students entering the law faculties of domestic universities, living before and studying in Uzbekistan, most of them

study for the same general education program (for with the exception of students of gymnasiums, lyceums and other specialized educational institutions with increased requirements). On the other hand, education in secondary school in one general education the program does not guarantee the same results for the fact of its completion. For the modern education system in Uzbekistan, a common situation is that the quality of teaching in Tashkent and large cities-megalopolises is an order of magnitude higher than the quality of teaching foreign languages in the regions, and even more so in small municipalities (villages, villages, urban settlements, etc.) ... As a rule, even foreign language teachers working in secondary educational institutions in large cities have more highly developed professional competencies than teachers in small towns.

All this leads to the fact that a certain proportion of students entering universities, in the program of studying the English language of which is the study of the professional component of the language - the professional the vocabulary and specifics of the style of the corresponding sublanguage cannot effectively study this block of knowledge, since they do not have the formed competencies of general education English. This aspect, of course, should be taken into account in the development of a comprehensive methodology for teaching English for students of legal specialties, within the framework of a particular university.

Another problem in developing a comprehensive methodology for teaching

English is the specifics of legal terminology in the framework of the regulatory legal acts of various countries. This is especially important for students whose profile area of study is international law. This aspect is very clearly reflected in the differences between terms of the same semantic meaning in the US and UK regulations. For example, for example, the terms "solicitor" and "barrister" exist only in British law, "counselor" - in the United States and Ireland.

Discussion

The entire foreign language course for law students must be taught exclusively in English. In many universities in Uzbekistan, in particular universities with an exclusively legal focus, this is a significant problem, since the process of communication outside the framework of educational tasks, as well as an explanation of grammatical, lexical and other issues, many teachers broadcast in Uzbekistan. In the modern methodology of teaching foreign languages, the main emphasis is on the formation of communicative competence. The communicative competence of a lawyer is as Dvorsevaya, A. (2018) defined "the ability specialist to carry out communication in the process of performing various legal actions and solving legal problems on the basis of specially formed knowledge and skill".

In this regard, the training of a lawyer in the course of the discipline "Foreign language in the field of jurisprudence" requires to teach students the language of the specialty and to form in them the skills and abilities necessary to perform professional activities in English: the

ability to freely navigate in texts legal content, make messages, conduct conversation and translate and interpret from English into Uzbek and from Uzbek into English within the framework of professional topics and prepare legal documents. The most effective methods for the formation and development of these competencies among law students are: debates, a round table, role-playing games. An example is the game "Expert Rights" when students are invited to participate in a simulated television program in the audience Legal Expert: one student is an expert in Uzbek law, the other in UK law. Their task is to answer questions from the audience. Necessary choose the host of the program who will announce the topic and represent the guests of the program (experts), guide the discussion, invite guests to ask their questions. Other students - guests of the program, whose task is to ask experts questions (2-3) concerning the law of Uzbekistan and Great Britain.

Before the role-playing game "Legal Advice", students are offered samples of a claim in the civil court of the United States and the claim to the Arbitration Court of the Republic of Uzbekistan. Students must study and compare the shape and structure, find the similarities and differences between these claims. And

then a role play is done: student A is a practicing lawyer; student B is a TV presenter. The studio receives calls from people (other students of the group) who are in difficult situations. The task of a lawyer is to help the caller solve the problem, in particular, give recommendations on drafting a claim. Using samples of claims, the callers draw up statements of claim (Kamshukova, L. S, 2017). The presented methods of forming students' communicative competencies in learning English can be carried out both in the form of an educational activities (in the course of classroom activities), and in the form of extracurricular activities. All in all, teaching ESP specifically, Legal English to the students of law university requires a lot of efforts and research from ESP teachers. All the activities and techniques mentioned above presented methods for the development of students' communicative competencies are aimed at the spoken practice of professional English, and in parallel, at the development knowledge of grammar, increase in vocabulary. To maximize the effect of teaching English for law students should be multifaceted. A comprehensive teaching methodology should include the maximum possible number of methods of classroom, independent and extracurricular work.

REFERENCES:

1. Azizova, S. V. (2016). *Features of professionally-oriented teaching English to students of a legal profile*. Pedagogical Journal, Volume N4, pp. 251-260.
2. Dvorsevaya, A. B. (2018). *Professional English for students of legal specialties*. Pedagogical Journal, Volume N1 (4), pp. 232-240.

3. Kamshukova, L.S. (2017). *On the question of the formation of foreign language competence of law students*. Science and education: new time, Vol.6(23), pp.365-371.
4. Mirgiiazova, M. M. (2019). Scientific approaches to teaching foreign languages. Молодой ученый, (47), 37-39.
5. Raufov, M. M. (2021). Elementary transformations in simultaneous translation. Academic research in educational sciences, 2(1).
6. Puzibayeva, N. R. (2021). ИНГЛИЗ ТИЛИ ДАРСЛАРИДА МАҚОЛ ВА МАТАЛЛАРДАН САМАРАЛИ ФОЙДАЛАНИШ УСУЛЛАРИ. In Conferences.